

Research Paper

Effectiveness of Youth Activator Bachelor in Rural Development Program on People Empowerment in Aceh Jaya and Sabang, Aceh Province

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ABSTRACT

PSP3 Program (Youth Activator Bachelor of Rural Development Program) is a prime program of the Ministry of Youth and Sport of the Republic of Indonesia to alleviate poverty in rural areas through youth pioneering role. The objective of the research was to observe the effectiveness of PSP3 Program on people empowerment in Aceh Jaya and Sabang, Aceh Province. The research was done from January until March, 2018. This is a qualitative research. The samples were respondents/informants who are in accordance with the research category. There were 65 (sixty five) respondents that were taken by employing purposive sampling technique; 5 (five) respondents from each of 13 (thirteen) villages in 2 (two) sub-districts involved in the empowerment of PSP3 Program in Aceh Jaya and Sabang. Questionnaires were also distributed to solve the second problem. A simple tabulation was performed to clarify and facilitate the data obtained and to produce its percentage. The results of the research demonstrated that the PSP3 Program in Aceh Province according to the provisions established by the Ministry of Youth and Sport of the Republic of Indonesia has been well implemented. All processes beginning from the selection process of location, socialization until assessment done by the Ministry of Youth and Sport have been in accordance with the General Guidelines of the conduct of PSP3. The effectiveness demonstrated by PSP3 Program concerning the Empowerment of People in Aceh Jaya and Sabang, Aceh Province according to the research results was that all processes carried out by the participants of PSP3 Program have effectively empowered the people in Aceh Jaya District and Sabang, Aceh Province; the program ran well until it ended in spite of some rooms for improvement for the success of PSP3.

Keywords: PSP3 Program, People Empowerment

INTRODUCTION

Poverty is now a global issue, meaning that poverty has become a world problem, almost in various parts of the world including in countries that have abundant natural resources, poverty remains a problem that demands serious attention. Poverty is a condition of economic and social inability to meet the needs of the living standards of the people of a region, this inability is characterized by low income to fulfill basic integrity such as clothing, food and shelter. Low income will affect the

average standard of living such as health, education and other social services.

This also happens in Indonesia, the problem of poverty is a central issue in the country, especially after Indonesia was hit by a multi-democratic crisis that peaked in the period 1997-1999, so poverty has resulted in low education, high health costs, no savings to invest, lack of access to services public, difficult employment and low social protection. The same thing does not only happen in cities but also felt in rural areas. In March 2015 the percentage of

poor people in rural areas was 14.21 percent, then fell in September 2015 to 14.09 percent and then increased by 0.02 percent in March 2016 to 14.11 percent and again declined in March 2017 to 13.93 percent. When referring to Farmer Exchange Rate (NTP) data which continues to decline from 102.55 in January 2016 to 101.47 in June 2016 (BPS, 2017). Various efforts have been made by the government in terms of poverty alleviation, but the level of poverty is still not resolved and gives a high value in Indonesia Poverty in Indonesia is more a form of structural poverty, because Indonesia naturally has enough potential and resources not to experiencing poverty. This structure causes the absence of even distribution, the development of the quality and creative power of the people in each development and the marginalization of the role and participation of the community in every development as indicated by the weakening of community participation (Mulyadi, M. 2015).

As an area located on the western tip of Indonesia, Aceh is a region that has large natural resources, both resources in the industrial sector, especially industrial forest products, plantations, and agriculture, such as oil palm, rubber, paper, and mining processing industries. However, the results of this industry have not developed optimally, even Aceh itself is known as one of the oil and gas producing regions, so Aceh has become one of the richest provinces in Indonesia after Papua and East Kalimantan, but this reality is not comparable to the level of community welfare. The latest data shows that Aceh is the 6th ranked poor population (population below the poverty line) throughout Indonesia until September 2017. The first to fifth positions are Papua, West Papua, East Nusa Tenggara, Maluku and Gorontalo (BPS, 2017). Coupled with the poorest regions on the island of Sumatra with a percentage of poor population of 17.60 percent, the population of 4.48 million in 2017, (BPS Aceh, 2017).

This situation is certainly surprising. In the midst of the special autonomy fund and the abundance of natural resources it turned out that it was not enough to raise Aceh's ranking to a more respectable position. The vulnerability of the situation of society in the socio-economic field can certainly lead them to a situation of conflict. Even if there is no vertical conflict, it can also conflict horizontally, (Rosnida, 2016). The phenomenon of poverty in Aceh generally occurs in rural areas, September 2017 The Central Bureau of Statistics says 18.36 percent of families in rural areas live below the poverty line and added 10.42 percent in urban areas (BPS Aceh, 2017). The low level of education and agriculture as the main economic activities in the family are also related to poverty occurring in Aceh. So that the development inequality between cities and villages is felt at this time. But the fundamental factor underlying poverty in Aceh is the conflict and tsunami which led to an increasing number of unemployed people. There are several areas in Aceh that have experienced this impact, one of which is Aceh Jaya District, Sabang City, which was targeted by the Youth Bachelor Program in Rural Development (PSP3) class of XXIV in 2014 to 2016.

Aceh Jaya Regency is the west coast of Sumatra coast with a coastline length of approximately 160 kilometers. Aceh Jaya Regency is bordered by Aceh Besar District and Pidie District in the North, Indonesian Ocean and West Aceh District in the South, West Aceh District in the East and with the Indonesian Ocean in the West. Aceh Jaya itself is a rural area that has abundant natural resources support, but still saves the problem of poverty. In the post-tsunami reconstruction rehabilitation process there were many social institutions of the International Non-Government Organization (INGO), as well as the National Government Organization (NGO) which were engaged in empowerment in Aceh, but their presence had not been able to overcome poverty significantly in Aceh Jaya. There are 13,100 poor people in Aceh

Jaya with a percentage of 15.01% of the population in Aceh Jaya (BPS Aceh Jaya, 2017).

Likewise, Sabang City, Sabang City is an archipelago located on the western tip of Aceh Province, which has natural resources that are not inferior to other regions in Aceh with the Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) nominated by the Construction Sector, the Large Trade and Retail Sector; Car Repair and Recycling, Government Administration, Defense and Mandatory Social Security and Pertanian, Forestry, and Fisheries sectors. However, the city of Sabang is inseparable from the problem of poverty, statistical data shows that from 2014, 17.02% of the people of Sabang City lived in the poverty line, 2015 poverty in the city of Sabang increased by 17.69% and again declined in 2016 with a percentage of 17, 33% of the total 5810 people (BPS Kota Sabang, 2017).

In 2014 the results of research conducted by Said Muniruddin concerning the Study of the Strategy for Accelerating Poverty Reduction in the Aceh Community: Sabang City, Faculty of Economics and Business, Syiah Kuala University. It is seen that the largest group of poor family heads in Sabang City is in old age. As many as 60 percent of poor family heads who were respondents in this study were men. While the remaining 40 percent are women, both those who are family heads and who represent the family head at the interview. The average age of poor family heads is 50.6 years. The survey results show that there are 70 percent of poor family heads in the age group above 40 years. The details, as much as 25 percent of poor family heads in the city of Sabang are at the age of 40-50 years. Then 24 percent are at the age above 60 years, and 21 percent are aged 50-60 years. While the heads of poor families are relatively young, 21-30 years, only 11 percent. Poverty in old age will certainly exacerbate the condition of overall family welfare. Because those who are elderly generally have more family members and dependents, (Said Muniruddin, 2015). On

the other hand, the development process is a process of humanizing humans. The success of development can not only be measured in terms of economic or physical growth but also must look at other aspects such as improving the quality of human resources, because the assessment based on economic growth tends to only consider macro targets, which basically will lead to various development imbalances, among others sharpening of spatial disparities, village-city disparities, structural inequalities, and so on.

At present poverty alleviation has become the agenda of many parties, both the central government and the regional government. The Government of Aceh, specifically the government of Aceh Jaya and the city of Sabang have sought several strategies to solve the problem of poverty and improve the welfare of the community. Many groups are involved in empowering the community both through relevant institutions interested in issues of empowerment and the government directly, such as the Ministry of Youth and Sports (Kemenpora) of the Republic of Indonesia. Through the central government policy the Ministry of Youth and Sports through the Bachelor Youth Program Driving the Development in Rural Areas (PSP3) is the flagship program of the Ministry of Youth and Sports which has been going on since 1989 and until 2014 has placed under 18,173 scholars throughout Indonesia. For example, during 2006-2013, the PSP3 program had reached 2478 villages, 1249 sub-districts and 440 districts to empower the community, especially village communities.

PSP3 is Kemenpora's flagship program in alleviating poverty in rural areas, through this program it is expected to have a significant impact on poverty alleviation, especially in rural areas. The PSP3 program was developed with the aim of accelerating rural development through the role of youth pioneering in various community activities in rural areas. These activities must directly influence the dynamics of the life of rural communities,

the development of the potential of youth resources, and at the same time improve the welfare of youth and rural communities. It is also an effort to foster community leadership and independence. This program is expected to make the village a center of growth that can improve the lives of the better people in the future. This commitment is important as part of reducing the accumulation of highly educated human resources in urban areas, so that the village community and youth are able to rise up to productive activities and in the end the village can become a driving force in national economic growth. The aim of the study was to find out the exact study of whether the Youth Undergraduate Program in Rural Development (PSP3) had fulfilled the criteria set by the Ministry of Youth and Sports in the framework of Empowering the Community of Aceh Jaya Regency and the City of Sabang in Aceh and analyzing the effectiveness of the Youth Bachelor Program. Rural Development (PSP3) in conducting Community Empowerment in Aceh Jaya Regency and Sabang City, Aceh Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Empowerment

Conceptually, empowerment or empowerment comes from the word power (power or empowerment). Talcott Person (1960) distinguishes power (Power) into two dimensions, namely distributive and generative. The distributive dimension of power is defined as the ability of a person or group to impose their will on others. Whereas the generative dimension of power is actions that enable the community or social unit to improve their ability to change their future which is done on their own choice (A.M.W. Pranarka & Vidhyandika 1996). Therefore the idea of empowerment comes into contact with the concept of power. Power is often associated with our ability to make other people do what we want, regardless of their wants and interests (Edi Suharto, 2010). In relation to community empowerment, many experts

have come to speak in this regard, one of which is (Payne in Sabirin, 2012), who argues that empowerment (empowerment) is essentially shown to:

"Helping clients to gain power to be able to make decisions and determine the actions they will take that are related to themselves, also reduce the effects of personal and social barriers in carrying out these actions carried out by increasing their ability and confidence to use the power they have, including through the transfer of power from the environment ". According to Sunyoto Usman (2008) there are at least two kinds of perspectives that are relevant to approaching the issue of community empowerment." (1) Perspectives that focus their attention on resource allocation (resource allocatin), and (2) perspectives that focus their attention on institutional appearance (institutional performance. "Meanwhile, Hukme and Tunr (1990) argue that empowerment encourages a process of social change that enables peripheral people who are powerless to exert greater influence in the political area both locally and nationally. The purpose of community empowerment is to build returning society as a place of important human experience, fulfilling human needs, and rebuilding structures in a welfare state, global economy, bureaucracy, inhuman professional elite and so on (Jim Ife & Frank Tesoriero, 2008) Empowerment refers to people's abilities, especially the elderly n and weak so they have inner strength or ability. First: fulfill their basic needs so that they have freedom, in the sense that they are not only free to express their opinions, but are free from hunger, free from ignorance, free from pain. The second: reaching productive resources that enable them to increase their income and obtain the goods and services they need; and third: participation in the development process and decisions that affect them (Sabirin, 2008).

During colonialism in the world in the report on the mission of community empowerment in Cambridge, England in

1948, community empowerment was defined by Colonial administrators as a movement to create a better life for the whole community; this covered all areas of district-building activities. The district is carried out both by the government and the private sector (Surjadi, 1975). The concept of empowerment was born as an anti-thesis towards the development model and the industrialization model that was not in favor of the majority people. This concept is built from the logical framework as follows: (1) that the process of concentration of power is built from the concentration of mastery of the production factor; (2) the concentration of the power of production factors will give birth to working and community societies that are peripheral entrepreneurs; (3) power will build knowledge systems, political systems, legal systems, and manipulative ideologies to strengthen and legitimize; and (4) the concept of knowledge systems, legal systems, political systems, and ideologies, systematically will create two groups of people, namely empowered communities and civil society (Erni in Prajono and Pranarka, 2012).

Strategies in Community Empowerment

According to Chin Benne (1961), without specifically pointing to community empowerment, introducing three strategies for change and underlying assumptions. The choice of strategy is racial-empirical, normative-reductive, or power-coercive depending on assumptions related to human nature, power relations, and community citizen attitudes and systems (Fredian Tonny Nasdian, 2014). In some situations, empowerment strategies can be carried out individually; although in turn the theory is also related to collectivity in the sense of linking clients with other sources or systems outside themselves. According to Edi Suharto (2009) in the context of empowerment it can be done through three levels of empowerment: micro, mezzo and macro.

1. Macro level. Empowerment is carried out on individual clients through guidance, counseling, stress

management, crisis intervention. The main goal is to guide or train the community in carrying out their life's tasks. This model is often referred to as a task-centered approach.

2. Mezzo level. Empowerment was carried out on a group of scavenger children. Empowerment by using groups as intervention media. Education and trainers, group dynamics, are usually used as a strategy in increasing awareness of knowledge, skills and attitudes in order to have the ability to solve problems faced.
3. Macro level. This approach is also called the large-system strategy, because the target of change is directed at a broader environmental system. Policy formulation, social planning, social action campaigns, lobbying, organization and conflict management are some of the strategies in this approach. Large system strategies view communities as individuals who have competition to understand their own situations, and to choose and determine the right strategy for action.

Various Approaches in Community Empowerment

Every process of community empowerment contains three elements, namely the existence of a change process, resource mobilization and community capacity building.

1. Process of Change

1. The factor that can be used to see the emphasis on human and community aspects in the concept of community development is understanding as a process of change. If theoretically changes in people's lives can impact regress or progress, changes in development are expected to impact progress. One indication of the willingness of change can be seen from the improvement in the standard of living or welfare of the community. Viewed from the other side, the needs that must be fulfilled also vary, not only

concerning physical needs but also mental and social needs (Suetomo, 2010). However, in essence, the meaning of fulfilling social needs converges in two main schools of thought. First, social welfare as a "development goal". In this thinking, social welfare includes not only the fulfillment of basic needs, but also the overall aspects of the quality of life, the second, placing social welfare in a limited sense, and even tends to be narrow. In this school of thought, the conception of social welfare is identical to the concept of a Western European welfare state which is a complement (complement) of Capitalism (Ah Maftuchan et.al, 2016).

2. Use of Resources

Increasing people's welfare can be seen from the increasing number of needs that can be met. In connection with efforts to meet these needs, there are resources and potential that can be utilized in every community. Therefore, community empowerment is often also referred to as an effort to create harmonious relationships between the resources available and the needs of the community. In realizing this process, what is needed is the ability to identify resources, then utilize and process them properly. Thus based on this view, identification of resources is a strategic step in the process of community empowerment. Therefore, identification of resources can function to lift resources that are still buried above the surface of social reality, so that they can be immediately utilized in the framework of living standards.

3. Community Capacity Development

According to Hoogvelt in Sutomo (2010), changes that occur in the development process in developing countries can be a change as a result of an evolutionary process, change because the results of the interaction in a broader scope or change due to the action. As mentioned above in community

empowerment, the main priority is given to efforts to build aspects of society and human aspects. One indication that there is already development in the aspects of society and the human aspect is that there is an increase in capacity, including the capacity to develop itself. Thus, if in the sense of community development in it contains the meaning of the process of change, where changes are whatever factors that drive it, including changes.

Paradigm of Community Development and Community Empowerment.

To achieve the goals and ideals of modernization, the community participation approach was developed in community development. According to Abbot in Sukmaniar (2007), the modernization theory was initially used by Western people who played a role in transforming the whole society from traditional and primitive to modern through continuous stages of improvement in economic growth. All community development concerns even intended for the community. But all methods, community development have their own characteristics. Community development is not only intended to foster the relationship and life of everyone who lives in a community, but also to build a community because each community unit has its own strength called community power by Nelson, W. in TaliziduhuNdraha (1990).

Community Development is a basic concept that underlines a number of terms that have been used for a long time, such as community resource development, rural development areas, community economic development, rural revitalization, and community based development. Community development describes the important meaning of two concepts: community, meaning the quality of social relations and development, changes towards planned and gradual progress. This meaning is important for the real meaning of community

development (Blackburn in Fredian Tonny Nasdian, 2014).

According to Suetomo (2010) community development is a process that is a community effort that is integrated with government authorities to improve socio-economic and cultural conditions of the community, integrate communities into national life and encourage more optimal

community contributions to national progress. Community development is used as an approach to community participation in the paradigm of modernization theory, while community empowerment is an approach in the context of dependency theory. The hierarchical relationship between these two theories can be seen in the following figure:

Sumber: Abbott, John dalam Sukmania, (2007.)

Figure 1. Paradigm of the "Community Participation Model" Approach

The theory of power relations and community participation according to Abbot (1996) is described in the form of a continuum where at one side the government is more open to community involvement in decision making, in other situations the government does not play a role. If the role of government does not exist (government closed), the role of the community will be high, this is the success stage of empowerment, but on the other hand also creates confrontation or approaches to physical strength, so that there is no development approach that can be implemented (Sukmaniar, 2007).

In Community Development contains efforts to increase participation and belonging (participating and belonging together) there are programs implemented and must contain elements of community empowerment of these elements, namely participation, sense of belonging and community empowerment can be created

strongly then transparency is needed in program implementation and the accountability of program implementers so that there was no misdirection and mismanagement, then the implementation of community development reminded several things that must be considered so that the programs implemented were successful.

Understanding of PSP3

The Undergraduate Youth Program Driving the Development in Rural Areas (PSP3) is the flagship program of the Ministry of Youth and Sports which has been going on since 1989 with the name of the Bachelor of Driving Rural Development Program (SP3) and has now changed its name to the Bachelor of Youth in Rural Development (PSP3). PSP3 has placed more than 19,173 scholars in all regions of Indonesia. For example, during 2006-2013, the PSP3 Program reached 2478 villages, 1249 sub-districts and 440 districts.

Scholars placed in the village in their duties to mobilize and assist the community, especially youth, are able to grow a variety of productive activities, especially in the fields of economy, education, health, and the environment. PSP3 has also been instrumental in helping and assisting village government activities such as: population administration, land and building taxes, structuring village assets and others. Including growing productive business units in the fields of agriculture, fisheries, small industries / handicrafts and trade services carried out by the community and directed at increasing the productivity of rural communities through developing community economic activities, based on the spirit of nationality.

Legal basis

- a. Law Number 13 of 2003 concerning Labor;
- b. Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System;
- c. Law Number 12 Year 2008 concerning the Second Amendment to Law Number 32 Year 2004 concerning Regional Government;
- d. Law Number 39 of 2008 concerning State Ministries;
- e. Law Number 40 of 2009 concerning Youth;
- f. Law Number 60 Year 2014 concerning Villages;
- g. Government Regulation Number 38 of 2007 concerning Division of Government Affairs Between the Government, Provincial Government and Regency / City Government;
- h. Government Regulation Number 41 of 2011 concerning Entrepreneurship Development and Youth Pioneering, and Provision of Youth Facilities and Infrastructure;
- i. Government Regulation Number 60 of 2013 Concerning Youth Entrepreneurship Capital Institutions;
- j. Presidential Regulation Number 91 of 2011 concerning Third Amendment to Presidential Regulation Number 47 of

2009 concerning Formation and Organization of State Ministries;

- k. Regulation of the Minister of Youth and Sports Number 0022 of 2010 concerning the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Youth and Sports in 2010 - 2014;
- l. Regulation of the Minister of Youth and Sports Number 193 of 2010 concerning the Organization and Work Procedure of the Ministry of Youth and Sports;

PSP3 Program Direction

Vision and mission

Vision

Become a flagship program in developing independent, productive and innovative Indonesian youth.

Mission

- a. Developing the potential and attitudes, as well as the behavior of youth to develop rural areas.
- b. Developing the potential of highly educated youth who have the character of leadership, pioneering and volunteerism to mobilize various potentials in rural areas for the welfare of society.
- c. Increasing community participation, especially youth in social, economic and information services through the role of initiation, facilitation and assistance in rural development programs.
- d. Developing youth Independence through the piloting of youth social and economic institutions in responding to the challenges of development in rural areas, introducing and developing communities and youth in the utilization and management of information technology

PSP3 Program Program Management

Responsible for PSP3 program

In order to optimize the implementation and increase the quality of supervision, the PSP3 Program is managed with a functional and tiered structure. At the central level, the person in charge of the program is the Deputy for Youth Development of the Ministry of Youth and

Sports of the Republic of Indonesia. While the technical person in charge is the Assistant Deputy of Youth Pioneering Deputy for Youth Development, who in the technical implementation of the program is assisted by the PSP3 Pokja Team and regional coordinators.

Regional Implementing Agency

The person in charge of PSP3 activities in the regions at the Provincial and Regency / City level is the Head of the Dispora / Agency that handles youth at the Provincial level.

Assistance Team

Regional Governments through Dispora / Institutions that handle provincial level youth propose names of Assistance Team candidates to the Deputy of Youth Ministry of Youth and Youth Development of Republic of Indonesia to be designated as Provincial Assistance Teams. The Assistance Team is tasked to assist Dispora / Institutions that handle youth in improving the effectiveness of the PSP3 program in the field. Coaching and monitoring activities are also carried out through internet information media (online), so that Kemenpora can supervise directly to PSP3 participants.

Forms of activity

The form of PSP3 assignment is individual, but will work in teams or groups within the scope of villages / sub-districts and districts / cities. In detail, these tasks include:

1. Mobilization:

- a. Identifying and mapping village potential in a participatory manner as a basis for planning programs and business activities that include identifying problems encountered, potential business alternatives, and various potential local and outside resources.
- b. Organizing the community (youth) in pioneering the establishment of local institutions (Joint Business Groups or Working Groups) as a forum for

communication and cooperation between citizens.

- c. Embed national insight into the community and especially young people in rural areas.
- d. Plan and socialize the idea of microfinance development (Savings and Loans Group, BMT) to the community.
- e. Growing people's interest in learning by utilizing communication and information media.

2. Field of Assistance:

- a. Encourage and develop the growth of micro-finance business units (savings and loans) in the form of (Cooperatives or BUMdes) that are built from, by and for the community (youth).
- b. Encouraging and fostering the self-supporting capital of village / kelurahan communities, especially youth in order to expand capital services to the community.
- c. Online dissemination (dissemination) of management excellence and institutional products for efforts to improve community welfare.
- d. Providing assistance and consultation to the village government in structuring village administration, increasing the resources of village officials to improving services to the community.
- e. Utilizing the functioning or availability of information access (internet media) that is healthy and productive in supporting community resource development.

3. Field of Independence:

- a. Pioneering and developing independent businesses involving young people who are integrated and become links with businesses run by the community in the fields of productive economy and or creative economy and information technology.
- b. Facilitate the implementation of leadership training activities for youth in order to prepare community cadres who can play a role in carrying out activities after the program ends.

PSP3 Program Target

- a. Availability of highly educated youth who have methodological and managerial skills as drivers of rural development.
 - b. The realization of cooperation and networking between youth, PSP3 with other parties in supporting rural development.
 - c. The implementation of productive activities in the productive economy and creative or microfinance economies (Savings and Loans Groups and BMT) which can support the scale of productive business activities of rural communities.
 - d. The implementation of village government activities that are effective in providing convenience and speed in service to the community.
2. The results of activities in the community include:
 - a. The community is aware of the PSP3 program in their village and knows the participants.
 - b. Growing public awareness to participate in the implementation of the PSP3 Program.
 - c. The development of community institutions in the village that support productive activities in the socio-economic and environmental fields.
 - d. The growth of microfinance institutions (credit) to support productive economic efforts in the community, especially youth in the village.
 - e. There is support and cooperation network with other resources (Government agencies, Private / BUMN, NGO sorother agencies) in realizing or developing business activities and national education.
 3. The sustainability of activities at the Community Level which includes:
 - a. Availability of cadres of leaders (local HR) prepared to replace the role of PSP3, so as to guarantee the sustainability of the program.
 - b. The functioning of local institutions (KUB / Koperasi / BUM Desa) in the activities and management of productive activities and management systems that can be carried out by community cadres even without the existence of PSP3.
 - c. Expansion of productive activities developed by PSP3 Participants to other regions by villages, regional governments and the business world.

Evaluation of PSP3 Implementation

Indicator of Success

The PSP3 program will be considered successful, if 3 (three) indicators can be fulfilled, namely:

1. The development of PSP3 Participants' capabilities which includes:
 - a. Able to interact, integrate and work with communities and other stakeholders to develop innovative ideas in productive activities in rural areas.
 - b. Able to develop joint business plans for the community (youth) in the field of productive socio-economic activities, microfinance institutions, education etc.
 - c. Able to organize and mobilize various local potentials as a basis in pioneering productive economic activities, microfinance, education and the use of information technology.
 - d. Able to document and report on conditions, developments, results and problems faced in the task systematically and analytically.
 - e. Able to develop education and understanding and cultivate national values in people's daily lives.
 - f. Able to use information technology to support rural development.

Achievement of PSP3 Implementation

In implementing the PSP3 program the level of achievement is periodically evaluated for each PSP3 participant, namely:

- a. The first 3 months after placement, evaluates whether the participants have made a mapping and initiated the 4 targets mentioned above, and made an activity planning program for 2 years.

- b. months after placement and have received initial capital, participants are evaluated whether they have implemented the results of the mapping and initiation and implemented the initial program for activities for 2 years.
- c. 12 months after placement, the program must be implemented in accordance with the targets set in the program of their activities.
- d. 18 months after placement, an evaluation of the overall program implementation is carried out.
- e. If points a and b are not implemented, participants will be evaluated to terminate their contracts as PSP3 participants.

PSP3 Participant Performance Assessment

The performance evaluation of PSP3 program participants at the assignment location was carried out incidentally and periodically by the Central and regional teams in an integrated manner with the mentoring process according to the guidelines issued by the Ministry of Youth and Sports.

1. The minimum assessment substance includes: the achievement of successful implementation of tasks, the level of community participation, the response of the government and the village community, innovations developed and factors that become obstacles in the implementation of the program.
2. The results of the performance assessment are used as one of the inputs for program managers to assess the improvement of the program implementation process, determine the awarding and determination of sanctions.

Strategy and Approach to the Operational Stage of the PSP3 Program Approach Strategy

In order to increase effectiveness and success in accordance with the objectives, the approach that must be taken by PSP3

Participants includes 5 (five) strategies, namely:

- a. Mapping (mapping). This is intended to determine the condition and potential of the Village which will be the location for the placement of the PSP3 program and the people who are assisted. In addition, it also establishes opportunities for cooperation with other institutions, both government, BUMN and private sector.
- b. Capacity building, aims to develop PSP3 resource potential and assisted communities by the District / City Dispora Team.
- c. Community empowerment is a strategy to empower the community in improving welfare.
- d. Network Development (networking), a strategy that seeks to build networks with other resources to support the achievement of program results.
- e. Program marketing (social marketing), a strategy to promote and disseminate the best activities (best practice) from PSP3 to the wider community through print, electronic and online media.

Definition of Effectiveness

In general, effectiveness is often associated with a success and the results achieved by the organization. In organization effectiveness is the main thing in measuring success in running an organization. The effective measurement of the organization is seen from the objectives and initial foundation of the objectives to be achieved. If the results obtained are in accordance with the targets that have been determined in the beginning, they are called effective. Handyaningrat (1994) said that effectiveness is a measure in terms of achieving predetermined goals. This means that the effectiveness of an organization must be measured by the main objectives that have been determined in the process of determining organizational goals and programs. In accordance with Permendagri Number 13 of 2006 the effectiveness is the achievement of program results with targets

that have been determined, namely by comparing outputs with results.

According to the Executive Summary the Effectiveness of Development Planning Study by the Research and Development Agency (2010) explains that the indicators of effectiveness in regional development planning are:

1. Time unit;
2. Unit of results;
3. Quality of work; and
4. Community satisfaction.

Based on several opinions above, the indicator of effectiveness is a benchmark in determining the level of achievement of a goal. Effective is an illustration that the goals achieved have been measured based on the results of the use. It is also very close to solving a problem, therefore effectiveness is sometimes not measured by how much money is needed, but rather focuses on optimizing problems that can be resolved. To see the effectiveness of the Youth Scholarship Program in Rural Areas (PSP3), the references used in this study are based on the General Guidelines for Undergraduate Youth Implementation Driving in Rural Development (PSP3) Ministry of Youth and Sports of the Republic of Indonesia force XXIV 2014.

MATERIALS & METHODS

This research uses descriptive research method with a qualitative approach to describe and analyze the Effectiveness of Bachelor of Youth Driving Development in Rural Areas (PSP3) on Empowerment of the Aceh Jaya Community and the City of Sabang, Aceh Province. As stated by Sugiyono (2008) that qualitative descriptive research seeks to describe and interpret the conditions and relationships that exist, opinions that are growing, ongoing processes, consequences that are happening, or trends that are developing. In addition, this research was also carried out by distributing questionnaires to respondents to get responses about empowerment carried out but not tested. The results will be presented in the form of simple tabulations

and used to see the frequency in the form of percentage data obtained from the distribution of questionnaires.

The research on the effectiveness of the PSP3 program took place in 7 villages in KruengSabe District, Aceh Jaya Regency and 6 Gampong in Sukajaya Sub-District, Sabang City, Aceh Province. 2014 to 2016 in Aceh Province. Aceh Jaya itself is a rural area that has abundant support of natural resources, and having problems with poverty which cannot be overcome, also the city of Sabang is an archipelago that still holds poverty in rural areas. The time of this research was conducted from January to March 2018.

The types of data used in this study are primary data and secondary data. Primary data obtained from direct research in the field in the form of observations and questionnaires containing statements and tangible numbers to look for percentages of each indicator or semi-structured statement and interview conducted to informants on the effectiveness of Youth Bachelor Driving Development in Rural Areas (PSP3). While secondary data is written references such as documents, other books relating to this research.

Data collection techniques needed in this study include:

1. Primary data, obtained through a series of questions posed to respondents through a questionnaire containing questions about the indicators of the effectiveness of the PSP3 program in this case the chosen sample is the community, which is involved in the empowerment process by PSP3 where 5 villages each. In addition, interview techniques were carried out to informants, namely the Head of the Aceh Province Youth and Sports Office, the Aceh Youth and Sports Agency and Sabang City, the Assistance Team of the Ministry of Youth and Sports and KeuchikGampong / Village Heads, village officials, communities and related agencies who supported in this study. Determination of informants in

this study is based on the consideration that informants know and have an understanding of empowerment by PSP3 in Aceh Province.

2. Secondary data, namely data obtained from the general guidelines for PSP3 implementation, PSP3 technical guidelines, monthly reports on activities, pilot funding reports and PSP3 participants' final reports.

When referring to the sampling technique in this study called the respondent / informant, it is more precisely to use purposive sampling because the informant set is an informant who is in accordance with a category of research (unit of analysis) because it is the step specified in sampling (Santori in Kaelan) , 2012). Purposive sampling is a sampling technique of data sources with specific considerations or objectives. These particular considerations or objectives, for example, people, informants or respondents are considered to be the most knowledgeable and masterful about what will be revealed in the study. For example, the person is a regional leader, community leader, religious leader or cultural figure, making it easier for researchers to explore the object under study (Sugiyono, 2008). For respondents of this study will be taken 5 (five) respondents for 13 (thirteen) villages from 2 (two) sub-districts involved in empowerment by PSP3 in Aceh Jaya Regency and Sabang City which amounted to 65 (sixty-five) people. In detail the sample distribution is as follows:

No	Sample group	Male	Female	Amount
1	Village apparatus	29	15	44
2	Yuoth Figure	11	4	15
3	Community Leader	3	3	6
Total				65

Source: Results of Research Data Processing

To answer the problem, qualitative data analysis is used as an analysis based on the work of grouping symbols other than numbers. The symbol is in the form of words, phrases, or sentences that indicate several categories. Input and output analysis

of qualitative data in the form of symbols, where the output is called verbal description. Miles and Huberman (1994) suggest that the activities in qualitative data analysis are carried out interactively and take place continuously in order to complete, so that the data is saturated. Data analysis activities, namely data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing / verification.

Whereas to answer the second problem formulation obtained from the distribution of questionnaires, to clarify and simplify the results of the data obtained, simple tabulations are conducted to find the percentage (Anas in Charles, 2013). Using the formula:

$$P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$$

Information:

P : Percentage

F : Frequency the percentage sought (Number of Respondents)

N : Amount of Frequency

100% : Standardization Numbers

The use of this analysis technique is used to measure the percentage of data obtained from distributing questionnaires about the indicators of the effectiveness of the PSP3 program on community empowerment that are determined and delivered to informants.

Table 2. Table of Answers to Questions

Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5		
Agree	4		
Disagree	3		
Disagree	2		
Strongly disagree	1		
Total		65 person	100%

To measure the quality of the data, the data that has been collected based on the perceptions of the respondents is quantified so that statistical tests can be carried out. Because of that reliability testing was conducted to designate the consistency and stability of the results of a particular measurement scale, the reliability of concentration on the problem of measurement accuracy and the results

(Sarwono Jonatan, 2006). While validity is a measure that shows that the measured variable is really the variable that the researcher wants to examine. (Zulganef in Charles, 2013).

Research requires true and valid data, for which validity tests are used by Sugionotiori (2008), the conditions used are the person correlation greater than r critical 0.3, if less than 0.3, the question points or instruments are r - the correlation is less than 0.3, it will be considered null or unused. Whereas according to Sekaran in Erlina, (2011) the level of how much a measure can be measured can be measured stably and consistently. An instrument is considered realistic if the instrument can be trusted as a data measuring instrument. Test reliability is done by using the formula croanbach's alpha. (Purwanto, 2007). Where the criterion of the value of croanbach's alpha is if alpha is smaller than 0.6, it is said that the research is bad, if it is around 0.7, it can be said that research can be accepted. If it is equal to or greater than 0.8, it can be said to be good research.

Or the criterion of reliability testing according to Gozali (2005) is that if Alpha is greater than 0.6 ($\alpha > 0.6$) then it can be said to be reliable, and if alpha is smaller than 0.6 ($\alpha, 0.6$) then it can be said no reliable.

Operational Definition of Variables

Operationally the variable needs to be defined which aims to explain the variable meaning of the research. Variables must be defined operationally so that the relationship between a variable and another is easier to find and measure it. Without operational variables, researchers will experience difficulties in determining the measurement of relationships between variables that are conceptual (Muhamad Mulyadi, 2012). The variable definitions in this study are as follows:

1. Effectiveness is how far the results have been produced both in time, quality in the organization and activities that have been carried out, which target has been set at the beginning of the formulation

of the formation of an organization or program.

2. The Bachelor Youth Driving the Development in Rural Areas is a Government program through the Ministry of Youth and Sports of the Republic of Indonesia in the development of rural communities by accelerating rural development through the role of youth pioneering in various community activities in rural areas.

Community empowerment is an effort to make people prosperous who experience problems both economically, socially, education and politically by utilizing available resources through community participation which is the center of empowerment.

RESULT

Validity and Reliability Test Results

The validity test in this study uses a critical r requirement of 0.3, if it is less than 0.3, the question points or instruments for which the correlation is less than 0.3 will be considered as null or unused. But if it is larger, the research instrument can be said to be valid. From the results of testing the validity of the research instrument using the SPSS statistical software, it can be concluded that all items in this study were declared valid with r -correlation each question obtained greater than 0.3.

Test reliability is done by using the formula Cronbach's alpha. If alpha is smaller than 0.6 then it is said that bad research, if around 0.7, can be said that research can be accepted. If it is equal to or greater than 0.8, it can be said to be good research. if the Alpha is greater than 0.6 ($\alpha > 0.6$) then it can be said to be reliable, and if alpha is smaller than 0.6 ($\alpha, 0.6$) then it can be said to be unreliable. From the results of the calculation of the reliability of the research instruments by using the SPSS statistical software, it can be concluded that the research instrument was declared reliable with a test result of 0.924 meaning that it was greater than 0.6 or above 0.7, the research could be accepted.

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.924	.924	13

Table 3. Validity and Reliability Test Results

Item-Total Statistics							
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Correlation	Item-Total	Squared Multiple Correlation	Multiple	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
P1	43.9077	60.991	.657		.615		.919
P2	44.1692	60.268	.702		.675		.917
P3	44.3846	60.428	.751		.728		.916
P4	44.4923	59.379	.741		.691		.916
P5	44.3077	59.623	.581		.447		.922
P6	43.5692	64.937	.352		.343		.928
P7	44.0923	60.398	.626		.667		.920
P8	44.4000	58.619	.714		.661		.916
P9	44.8154	58.403	.766		.656		.914
P10	44.3538	61.357	.569		.613		.922
P11	44.7846	58.422	.757		.736		.915
P12	44.6923	57.841	.725		.712		.916
P13	44.7692	57.149	.746		.624		.915

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing, 2018

Effectiveness of Undergraduate Youth Programs Driving Rural Development (PSP3) Against Community Empowerment in Aceh Jaya Regency and Sabang City Aceh Province

Empowerment concerns various fields of life which include physical, social, economic and political as stated by Suharto (2009) that empowerment as a goal refers to the conditions or outcomes to be achieved by a social change; namely people who are empowered, have the power or have the knowledge and ability to fulfill their daily needs, both physical, economic and social, such as having self-confidence, being able to express aspirations, have a livelihood, participate.

This is in line with the assessment of the effectiveness of community empowerment carried out by PSP3 in the province of Aceh which examines the impact of the community empowerment process on changing community conditions by using indicators based on assessments

from the Ministry of Youth and Sports of the Republic of Indonesia.

The Bachelor of Youth Driving the Development in Rural Areas (PSP3) is a strategic program and mainstay of the Ministry of Youth and Sports which has multiple effects, among others; regional development, economic development and employment. In 2011, PSP-3 numbered 1,000 people for 33 provinces, in 2012 the increase in youth productivity in rural areas amounted to 827 people, class XXIII who were recruited in 2013 for a 2-year assignment were participants I who were recruited strictly and received a briefing in collaboration with Pusdik Rindam Jaya Jakarta. Of the total participants who participated in the debriefing in September 2013 as many as 811 people, then those who passed and were placed in the village were as many as 794 people. This means that 17 people failed because of their lack of commitment and capacity to carry out their roles and functions as drivers of village development, (2017 Kemenpora Report).

The development of PSP3 Participants' capabilities includes:

Table 4. Able to establish communication, interact and collaborate with communities and other village leaders to develop innovative ideas in productive activities in rural areas			
Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	22	34
Agree	4	34	52
less Agree	3	7	11
Disagree	2	1	1.5
Strongly disagree	1	1	1.5
Total		65 person	100%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 1

Based on Table: 4 above shows that 52% of respondents answered agreeing about the ability of PSP3 participants in establishing communication, integration and collaborating with the community and other village leaders, to develop innovative ideas in productive activities in rural areas, 34% answered strongly agree and response that giving a very disagreeing rating of only 1%.

Bernard and Garry (in Nasor. M) explained that community empowerment cannot be separated from interpersonal communication with the community, because this communication has the main roles and tasks to motivate the community to be able to act more disciplined at work. The effectiveness of this communication will be easier to give a strategic direction that logically shapes a culture of discipline in society. Bernard explained that this communication in addition to conveying information, ideas, ideas, or skills, also through symbols would be able to change behavior.

From the explanation above, it can be seen that PSP3 participants are able to establish communication and integrate with the community in formulating productive economic ideas. Musriadi 2014-2016 RI Kemenpora Assistance Team revealed that: "Actually the PSP3 program is an icon of the Kemenpora program, meaning that

before the launch of the program there were stages that were carried out based on guidelines and operational guidelines, meaning that in the guideline explained various criteria and procedures for implementing the PSP3 program itself, concerning questions This has been accommodated to some extent in the PSP3 initial recruitment process, they must be able to interact with the community and also they have intrapersonal intelligence, of course they have a special obligation to interact with the community, so they interact then what is the PSP3 program series will be done well".

According to Sabirin, Village Secretary (Sekdes), Keutapang Village, Aceh Jaya Regency revealed that as long as the PSP3 participants were in Aceh Jaya Regency, the level of activity in planning productive economic activities and social activities was seen in the formation of groups with communities and also moving youth in productive economic activities. "As long as they (PSP3 participants) here they are very active in mobilizing their youth organizations to increase the effectiveness of business groups with the community, which is the condition of Aceh Jaya district which is currently potentially in animal husbandry and agriculture activities," he said.

Table 5. Able to develop a joint business plan for the community (youth) in rural areas in the field of productive socio-economic activities, microfinance institutions, education

Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	14	22
Agree	4	34	52
less Agree	3	13	20
Disagree	2	4	6
Strongly disagree	1	0	0
Total		65 person	100%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 2

Based on Table: 5 shows that the community considered 52% of PSP3 participants agreed to develop a joint business plan for rural (youth) communities in productive socio-economic activities, microfinance institutions, education, 22% answered strongly in agreement, so that the data above shows that firstly PSP3 has the ability to develop programs that will be

carried out both social, productive economic programs and educational institutions.

Arranging a business plan is an activity that expresses confidence in the ability of a business to succeed the business, the preparation of a plan of empowerment activities will enable us to see clearly whether the business to be run later has a high prospect of success. Planning for

empowerment activities must also be based on community needs for the existence of goods and services offered, so business planning must be based on market demand. The preparation of a business plan on the PSP3 program is important as a guiding basis for determining profitable future business activities. The preparation of a logical plan and based on information from the community allows the goal to be achieved effectively, and efficiently.

From the results of the above explanation, it shows the ability of PSP3 participants in developing a joint business plan for the youth (youth) in the field of productive socio-economic activities, microfinance institutions; education shows success in the implementation of the PSP3 program itself. This stage is carried out when the initial period of placement of PSP3 participants in the village becomes the object of dissemination.

As stated by Jalaluddin as the PSP3 Program Assistance Team the Ministry of Youth and Sports said that the initial planning process carried out by PSP3 participants was in accordance with PSP3 guidelines and operational guidelines set by the Ministry of Youth and Sports, meaning PSP3 participants in the planning process to mobilize innovative activities, PSP3 participants made initial assessment / initial mapping of potential in the village itself, so that the program produced was in accordance with available resources in the village, "PSP3 program planning was very good in accordance with the planning in the technical guidelines / guidelines PSP3, then we see from the planning carried out in accordance with the prospects in Aceh Jaya and Sabang City".

Fitria Secretary of Paya Village Seunara, Sabang City also revealed that the PSP3 program planning process was also included during the village Development Meeting (Musrembang), where programs proposed by PSP3 participants became mid-term village programs, so that the involvement of PSP3 participants dominated the formulation. the program that was carried out, "they were involved in the musrembang and other activities, drawing up a plan in the musrembang they proposed" he said.

However, it was different from what Muhammad said. The village head of KutaTimu, Sabang City, revealed that, in the implementation of planning for innovative activities in GampongKutaTimu, PSP3 participants were unable to formulate programs that had a positive impact on the community so that the formulation of the program was not in accordance with expectations of the community, "Concerning with PSP3 which is placed in KutaTimugampong, thank God, in principle, it does not object and we hope that with the existence of PSP3, there will be activities that are innovation that are mainly in the community sector, but this really has nothing to do with the community".

However, from interviews and observations, the authors did that the ability of PSP3 participants in developing joint business plans for rural (rural) communities in the field of productive socio-economic activities, microfinance institutions, education was successful because of innovative activities carried out by PSP3 participants both in agriculture, creative economy and other activities.

Table 6. Able to organize and mobilize various local potentials as a basis in pioneering productive economic activities, microfinance, education and the use of information technology.

Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	7	11
Agree	4	33	51
less Agree	3	23	35
Disagree	2	1	1.5
Strongly disagree	1	1	1.5
Total		65 Person	100%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 3

From Table: 6. above shows that in organizing and mobilizing various local potentials as a basis in pioneering productive economic activities, microfinance, education and information technology utilization 51% answered agree, but 23% of respondents answered disagree and 11% answered strongly agree . In mobilizing the local potential of PSP3, it is able to mobilize various local potentials of villages where PSP3 participants are placed. As stated by Jalaluddin, the Ministry of Youth and Sports Assistance Team in utilizing the local potential of PSP3 Participants has the ability to utilize good potential, natural resources and human resources.

"If we take advantage of local posts, we can see that 50% can run, meaning that we can see that some regions can raise unproductive government programs to be productive, to be made in the processing of local wisdom from the community itself. For example, Kota Sabang has unproductive swamp, with the existence of PSP3 they

make the water hyacinth into a bag or souvenir, or we see from another point of view, the potential of pesticides in the South West region, they communicate with the government so that they can give rise to various advantages Local products such as chips are supported from packaging, from processing fish made to jerky. There is indeed and real production done by the community "

The main principle in developing the concept of community empowerment carried out by PSP3 emphasizes the bottom up approach. Many activities carried out by PSP3 participants in both the City of Sabang and in the District of Aceh Jaya in the utilization of natural resources. Sabirin, Secretary of the Keutapang Village, Aceh Jaya District, also said that in PSP, PSP3 participants had many activities that had great potential in their placement villages such as fish farming, cattle fattening, biogas and poultry that had good potential in Aceh Jaya.

Table 7. Able to develop education and understanding and cultivate national values in people's daily lives.			
Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	9	14
Agree	4	24	37
less Agree	3	28	43
Disagree	2	3	4.5
Strongly disagree	1	1	1.5
Total		65 person	100%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 4

In table 7. concerns with developing education and understanding and cultivating national values in people's daily lives. 43% of respondents answered disagreeingly, while 37% answered agree and 14% answered strongly agree. The purpose of planting national values in the community, some people, especially among the youth, have decadence of national values. To anticipate this situation, the PSP3 program can be the front guard in building the spirit and national values for youth and society. Therefore young scholars as educated young people are expected to be able to invite rural youth to increase the spirit of nationalism and develop its potential to advance rural areas.

But from the results of the analysis in the field, it can be seen that in the planting of national values it has not run optimally, but in the education sector PSP3 participants are able to become a driver in the world of education, both school and youth education, as explained by Roni Zariansyah PSP3 Dispora of Sabang City that PSP3 is in the implementation of national values through education in the City of Sabang, PSP3 participants conduct training of the Indonesian Red Cross Youth and teach national values in Scout activities in schools, "Cadre of young Indonesian Red Cross cadres (PMI) and also the Scouting they are doing, "he said. In addition to the planting of national values, the cultivation

of entrepreneurial values carried out by PSP3 participants to foster interest in entrepreneurship, especially the young, because in its understanding entrepreneurship education is a conscious effort to prepare and equip students with a life attitude that has courage, courage, virtue and responding to every challenge of life by prioritizing on one's own strength, through ademis, non-academic activities, training, and guidance, (GunawanHari, H. 2000).

Table 8. Able to use information technology to support rural development.

Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	19	29
Agree	4	17	26
less Agree	3	25	39
Disagree	2	2	3
Strongly disagree	1	2	3
Total		65 person	100%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 5

From the table: 8. above 39% of respondents answered that they did not agree with PSP3 participants in using information technology to support rural development, 29% answered strongly agree, 26% answered agreed, 3% answered disagree and 3% answered strongly disagree.

The use of technology in rural areas is a carrying capacity for the progress of a village. The presence of technology in the village, indirectly enhancing production capabilities, providing added value to leading local commodities (local content), creating jobs and increasing community income. Not only that, technology creates independent business groups capable of productive economic activities. So that technology makes the village progress.

In general, technology that is widely absorbed and used by rural communities is Appropriate Technology (TTG). The most basic characteristic of TTG is that it can be made at a relatively cheap cost, how to make it very easy, and use local resources. The types of TTG that are widely used tend to be tools or machines that support the agricultural, livestock, fisheries, health, food processing, water management, sanitation and waste sectors, management of food, medicinal plants and so on. Technically, TTG is a bridge between traditional technology and advanced technology.

In Aceh Jaya and the City of Sabang, the use of technology in accelerating development in rural areas has been carried out by PSP3 participants, although there are some obstacles that make it constrained in the process of using technology in rural development, in Aceh Jaya itself. he said that PSP3 participants helped in the use of appropriate technology in the village, one of which was the creation of waterwheel, compost and bio-gas had provided great benefits to the target communities of the PSP3 participants themselves, "mobilizing the economic field of society in terms of compost "He also makes community income products in the field of bio gas and windmills," he said. In the City of Sabang itself, the use of technology for rural progress was also carried out as explained by RoniZariansyah, the companion of the Sabang City PSP3 Dispora program. inSabang City ". Embedding websites and teaching information technology to children is a way for the Sabang City PSP3 in carrying out rural development through the role of information technology.

The results of activities in the community include:

Table 9. The community is aware of the PSP3 program in their village and knows the participants.

Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	40	62
Agree	4	20	31
less Agree	3	3	4
Disagree	2	2	3
Strongly disagree	1	0	0
Total		65 Person	100%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 6

In the table: 9. shows that 62% strongly agree about the community knowing the PSP3 program in their village and getting to know the participants, 31% answered agreeing, 4% of respondents answered that they did not agree with 3% they did not agree.

From the table above shows that the community knows the program and also knows the whereabouts of the PSP3 participants themselves, in the Ministry of Youth and Sports in the initial screening process in the city district, has introduced and socialized the program intensively to the community so that the program PSP3 is known by the public, district / city governments, sub-district governments, and village governments who are interested in being targeted by the program. So that it fosters a common understanding of the purpose, objectives, and procedures for implementing the PSP3 program.

Program socialization and dissemination are not only for selection purposes, but also in the framework of broadly introducing the PSP3 program. Therefore, socialization is also in the form

of a variety of innovation activities and various other best practices which are the real work of Bachelor Youth. Dissemination and dissemination is carried out by distributing circulars, posters, booklets, leaflets, holding discussions, and advertising / publication of information in print, electronic, social media and various activities and festivals.

In the process of implementing the program carried out by PSP3 in the holding village, the process of introducing the community was carried out, the introduction and socialization was also accompanied by the assistance team of the Ministry of Youth and Sports and also the village apparatus of the PSP3 participants themselves. The process is so that the community knows the PSP3 Participants who are in the placement village well, in addition, the process of welcoming PSP3 participants is done through customary processes, as stated by Alqudri Geuchik Gampong Sentosa, Aceh Jaya Regency treat them as guests, we welcome the traditional pesujuk (fresh flour), "he said.

Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	19	29
Agree	4	29	45
less Agree	3	14	21.5
Disagree	2	2	3
Strongly disagree	1	1	1.5
Total		65 person	100%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 7

From Table 10. above shows that 45% of respondents answered the growing public awareness to participate in the implementation of the PSP3 program, 29% answered strongly agree, 21.5% answered disagree and 3% answered disagree.

It is seen that, there is public awareness to take part in the PSP3 program in implementing community empowerment programs, both in Sabang City and in Aceh Jaya Regency, but in the field several obstacles were encountered when the program was implemented, including the involvement of the community as a whole. the program implemented by PSP3, the

community at the beginning of the introduction of the program was apathetic, but after the program took place, the community's interest in participating in the program was carried out. As stated by Jalaluddin, the Assistance Team of the Ministry of Youth and Sports revealed that: "There are some regions that are indeed PSP3 when they first invited village officials, the community and also invited leaders to introduce PSP3 participants and the PSP3 program itself, but in reality the field was very heavy, and also what we found in the field was that , PSP3 is the one who invites the public to tell the public and

he also comes to the community when there are introductory activities, then it is proven and the work of PSP3 then the community invites PSP3 to help in various fields in the community, both of which have roles that At the same time as the process progressed, at the beginning there was no one who responded and then did not know, so that is where we assisted the community to introduce PSP3 products themselves, indeed it was difficult at the beginning itself but after passing 6 (six) months, the process is very easy because it has been proven by k the existing information from PSP3 ".

Likewise what was conveyed by El-Fakri Acting (PLT) of the Head of Youth Organization Empowerment of the Aceh Province Youth and Sports Agency who was responsible for the PSP3 program from 2008 to 2016, he stated that, for the involvement of the community in implementing the PSP3 program then there must be an example done by PSP3

participants, so as to make the community's attraction in participating in the program implemented, "PSP3 gives an example first and then the participants follow it" he concluded. But the difference delivered by Al-QudriGeuchikGampongSentosa, revealed that there were some participants in presenting programs that were less interested in the community, so that people were reluctant to be involved in the empowerment process, because the program was monotonous and had been carried out by the community. alone.

"Actually, people want to participate only, but we want to do the program's explanations. So after people hear their exposure seems to be mediocre, there is nothing extraordinary about the program they offer. Because it has actually been running in our village. What else are we as a village in the middle of the capital city of Aceh Jaya Regency, "he said.

Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	12	19
Agree	4	27	41.5
less Agree	3	19	29
Disagree	2	6	9
Strongly disagree	1	1	1.5
Total		65 person	100%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 8

From table: 11. shows that 41.5% of the community agrees to the development of community institutions in the village that support productive activities in the socio-economic and environmental fields in rural areas. 29% answered disagreeingly, 19% of respondents answered strongly agree and 9% did not agree.

From the results of the respondents' answers above, it shows that the existence of social and economic institutions built by the existence of PSP3 in implementing programs in rural areas, some of these institutions were built with the aim of increasing sustainable socio-economic activities after the PSP3 program ended. This institution is formed to be self-supporting carried out by PSP3 participants

in the community. However, in the formation of this institution, it was not entirely done by PSP3 participants, only how many villages were in Aceh Jaya and in Sabang City who did so.

RoniZariansyah Assistant to PSP3 Dispora, Sabang City said that. "Economic institutions, if the economic institutions they form are in Gampong, Ateuh City, SovenirPiyoh (Acehnese souvenirs), and the local youth they invited to join in the PSP3 activities for the establishment of cooperative cooperation with the community".

However, the different delivered by El-Fakri said that this program in parts of Aceh was only incidental, there was no seriousness in the empowerment process

carried out by PSP3 participants, so that the program implemented was not able to accommodate the interests of the wider community, there was no process sustainability that can be done by the community where PSP3 is placed.

From the results of the above explanation, it shows that there are not

many financial institutions built by PSP3 participants, this is due to various limitations both in terms of capital and existing potential, so that economic development is not well developed in the PSP3 placement village itself.

Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	6	9
Agree	4	16	25
less Agree	3	33	51
Disagree	2	8	12
Strongly disagree	1	2	3
Total		65 person	100%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 9

From the table: 12. shows that 51% of the community disagrees with the growth of microfinance institutions (credit) to support productive economic efforts in the community, 25% answer agree, 12% answer disagree and 9% answer strongly agree.

The results of the respondents' responses indicated that more than 50% of the community responded in disagreement to the activities of PSP3 participants in the development of microfinance institutions (credit) to support productive economic efforts in the community, many factors in the development of microfinance institutions in the community, according to the

results of the analysis of researchers are caused by:

1. the limited capital finance of the ministries of Youth and Sports, the Ministry of Youth and Sports only provides Rp. 20,000,000, - in 2 years and divided into several disbursement terms.
2. Limited time owned by PSP3 participants in building a strong network in developing microfinance activities.
3. Limited ability of participants in terms of microfinance management in the community.

The Sustainability of Activities at the Community Level which includes:

Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	12	18
Agree	4	27	42
less Agree	3	21	32
Disagree	2	5	8
Strongly disagree	1	0	0
Total		65 person	100%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 10

In the table: 13. relating to the support and network of cooperation with other resources (Government agencies, Private / BUMN, NGOs or other agencies) in realizing or developing business activities and national education there is that, 42% of respondents answered agreeing to the support and network of cooperation with other resources (Government agencies,

Private / BUMN, NGOs or other agencies) in realizing or developing business activities and national education carried out by PSP3 participants.

In principle, the PSP3 program is one of the assets that drives the acceleration of development which is expected to be able to develop a productive and innovative work culture and realize cooperation and

networking with the principle of togetherness and kinship. (Kemenpora, 2014)

Implementation of cooperation carried out by PSP3 in the implementation of the empowerment process in various forms, both in terms of human resource cooperation, in material and collaborative activities, is aimed at carrying out sustainable empowerment in the community. Cooperation carried out by PSP3 for the sustainability of the empowerment process as revealed by El-Fakir that the Ministry of Youth and Sports strongly encourages cooperation between PSP3 and other institutions in the process of community empowerment, "We always encourage them, support them so they don't

just focus on us, on the ministry especially the Dispora".

Jalaluddin also revealed that, "support exists, but the regional government and city government only carry out business development activities, from NGOs and the government to support PSP3 activities, the most of which is cooperative service but indeed there must be real work". RoniZariansyah "Collaborating with the community to build partners, their two months of movement was the Indonesian Red Cross (PMI) branch of Sabang City to invite partners and also from PMI to respond, to other business ventures with owners of souvenirs to design the souvenirs"

Table 14. Availability of cadres of leaders (local HR) prepared to replace the role of PSP3, so as to guarantee the sustainability of the program.

Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	7	11
Agree	4	15	23
less Agree	3	34	52
Disagree	2	7	11
Strongly disagree	1	2	3
Total		65 person	100%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 11

From table 14. above shows that, 52% of respondents answered in disagreement with the availability of cadres of leaders (local HR) who were prepared to replace the role of PSP3, so as to guarantee the sustainability of the program, 23% answered agreeably and 11% answered strongly agree.

From the results of the above percentage, it can be seen that PSP3 has not had a significant impact on the availability of cadres of leaders fostered by PSP3, both economic, social and religious institutions. PSP3 should be able to create human resources cadres in the placement village. The aim is for the sustainability of the program that has been carried out by PSP3 participants during the process of implementing tasks in the village. The success of the program is very important where the planned program will be continued by the cadres of available human resources.

It was also said by Musriadi, the Assistance Team of the Ministry of Youth and Sports explained that:

"Actually, this program is the one who must be the target. The target for regeneration and regeneration is what they do, say they want to create a program, the activity does not belong to PSP3, but belongs to the community when they leave it, whatever the form of activities whether the fields of agriculture, maritime affairs and all fields carried out will be generated society. And one of them is PSP3's vision is the independence of the community and pioneering, it has become the target of PSP3 especially young people not the general public, but youth are the target of empowerment".

However, there are several villages where the PSP3 program is still carried out by the community in the village, as stated by Jalaluddin: "If we look at some PSP3 programs in the community, it is still

continued by PSP3, such as fish farming still running, today there are still products marketed in the community. "Haryanto, Secretary of Gampong, Ateuh City, Sabang

stated that: "Perkaderan is the establishment of tourism conscious cadres, in Sabang especially marine tourism, approaching local and foreign tourism".

Table 15. The functioning of local institutions (KUB / Koperasi / BUM Desa) in activities, management of productive activities and management systems that can be carried out by community cadres even without the existence of PSP3.

Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	8	12
Agree	4	22	34.5
less Agree	3	23	35
Disagree	2	10	15.5
Strongly disagree	1	2	3
Total		65 person	10000%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 12

From table: 15. above shows that 35% of respondents answered that they disagreed with the functioning of local institutions (KUB / Koperasi / BUM Desa) in activities, management of productive activities and management systems that could be carried out by community cadres despite the absence of PSP3, 34% answered agree and 15% answered disagree, 12%

answered strongly agree and 3% answered strongly disagree.

From the results of the author's observation in the field, it shows that the absence of a running agency carried out by PSP3 shows that the lack of regeneration carried out by the PSP3 participants themselves had an impact on the failure in the process of forming an optimal running institution.

Table 16. Expansion of productive activities developed by PSP3 Participants to other regions by villages, regional governments and the business world.

Criteria	Score Criteria	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage %
Strongly agree	5	8	12
Agree	4	19	29
less Agree	3	25	38.5
Disagree	2	10	15.5
Strongly disagree	1	3	5
Total		65 person	100%

Source: Questionnaire Results, No. 13

From table 16. above shows that 38.5% of respondents answered disagree, 29% answered agree, 15.5% answered disagree, 12% answered strongly agreed and 5% answered strongly disagreed about the expansion of productive activities developed by PSP3 Participants to other regions by the village, local government and the business world.

From the above percentage shows that PSP3 participants are still not optimal towards the expansion of productive activities carried out by PSP3 participants even though in the process of placing PSP3 participants put a zone for the collaboration process between PSP3 participants themselves, as revealed by Musriadi said that:

"At the beginning of their determination there were zones of sub-districts and village zones, in those zones there were youths in village A and youth in their village B that had to react because each of these participants had to make innovations in the activities they carried out, so they became models, say in village A they create a model with their potential, so that it becomes an icon and will become a positive value that is utilized in other sub-districts "

So also said by Jajalaluddin the Aisten Team of the Ministry of Youth and Sports:

"If we look at it today, it depends on the prospect, if in the area, when there is no prospect for development, we have to find a neighboring location, but we can see the

system today even in other districts. this community was invited to give a contribution and capital was provided with initial capital, but when the land was insufficient we had to shift to another land. This means that the goal is deep in helping village governments, district governments and the central government, but the main ones are the regions themselves, but are allowed to do empowerment in other areas "

DISCUSSION

The entire explanation of the results above shows that most of the implementation of the PSP3 Program runs well but there are several aspects that are not effective, one of which is the availability

of cadres of leaders (local HR) prepared to replace the role of PSP3, so as to guarantee the sustainability of the program. microfinance (credit) to support productive economic efforts in the community, and the expansion of productive activities developed by PSP3 Participants to other regions by the village, regional government and business world. Many factors underlie the ineffectiveness of the three things mentioned above, including the limited time possessed by PSP3 participants in the empowerment process, the availability of a budget for a limited empowerment process and the ability of PSP3 participants to empower well based on criteria that have been explained above.

Table 17. Criteria for Effectiveness of Undergraduate Youth Program Driving Rural Development (PSP3) Against Community Empowerment in Aceh Jaya Regency and Sabang City Aceh Province after grouping

No	Description	Effectiveness	
		Score (%)	Category
1	Able to establish communication, interact and cooperate with the community and other village leaders to develop innovative ideas in productive activities in the countryside	4.46	Very effective
2	Able to develop a joint business plan for the (youth) community in the fields of productive socio-economic activities, microfinance institutions, education	3.36	Effective
3	Able to organize and mobilize various local potentials as a basis in pioneering productive economic activities, microfinance, education and the use of information technology.	3.27	Effective
4	Able to develop education and understanding and cultivate national values in people's daily lives.	3.7	Effective
5	Able to use information technology to support rural development.	3.24	Effective
6	The community is aware of the PSP3 program in their village and knows the participants.	3.66	Effective
7	Growing public awareness to participate in the implementation of the PSP3 Program.	3.73	Effective
8	The development of community institutions in the village that support productive activities in the socio-economic and environmental fields	4.5	Very effective
9	The growth of microfinance institutions (credit) to support productive economic efforts in society	3.75	Effective
10	There is support and cooperation network with other resources (Government agencies, Private / BUMN, NGOs or other agencies) in realizing or developing business activities and national education.	3.56	Effective
11	Availability of cadres of leaders (local HR) prepared to replace the role of PSP3, so as to guarantee the sustainability of the program.	3.67	Effective
12	The functioning of local institutions (KUB / Koperasi / BUM Desa) in the activities and management of productive activities and management systems that can be carried out by community cadres even without the existence of PSP3.	3.89	Effective
13	Expansion of productive activities developed by PSP3 Participants to other regions by villages, regional governments and the business world.	4.15	Very effective
	Total	48.94	Effective
	Average	3.76	

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research on the effectiveness of the Youth Bachelor Program in the Development of Rural Development (PSP3) towards the empowerment of the people of Aceh Jaya Regency and the City of Sabang in Aceh, the following conclusions were obtained:

1. In the implementation of the PSP3 Program which concerns the conformity of implementation with the provisions established by the Ministry of Youth and

Sports of the Republic of Indonesia in Aceh Province, it is running well. From the process of site selection, socialization until the assessment process by the Ministry of Youth and Sports runs according to the General Guidelines for the Implementation of PSP3.

2. The effectiveness of PSP3 Program in Aceh Jaya Community Empowerment and Sabang City of Aceh Province from the results of the research conducted

shows that from all the processes carried out by PSP3 participants having effective value in empowering the people of Aceh Jaya Regency and Sabang City in Aceh Province, the programs implemented from the whole can running to the maximum until the deadline of the program takes place, but there are some things that become a reference again about the success of PSP3 itself.

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